

worm

**Waste in humanitarian Operations:
Reduction and Minimisation**

D6.1. Limitations of bio -based solutions

Date of delivery: **31/10/2025**

Authors: **Joseph, Sarah; Besiou, Maria**

Institution: **KLU (DE)**

**Funded by the
European Union**

DOCUMENT TRACK INFORMATION

PROJECT INFORMATION	
Project acronym	WORM
Project title	Waste in humanitarian Operations: Reduction and Minimisation
Starting date	01/01/2024
Duration	24 months
Call identifier	HORIZON-CL6-2023-CIRCBIO-01
Grant Agreement No	101135392

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION	
Deliverable number	D6.1
Work Package number	WP6
Deliverable title	Limitations of bio-based solutions
Authors	Joseph, Sarah (KLU) Besiou, Maria (KLU)
Due date	31/10/2025
Submission date	30/10/2025
Type of deliverable	R
Dissemination level	PU

REVISION TABLE

VERSION	CONTRIBUTORS	DATE	DESCRIPTION
V0.1	Sarah Joseph (KLU)	10/10/2025	First draft
V0.2	Maria Besiou (KLU)	15/10/2025	Updated draft internally reviewed
V0.3	Lucie Guilleateau (Euronovia)	20/10/2025	Formatting
V1	Gyöngyi Kovács (Hanken)	30/10/2025	Final version for submission

LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	FULL NAME
ACF	Action Against Hunger
BBM	Bio-based materials
CLD	Causal Loop Diagram
FBM	Fossil-based materials
GHG	Greenhouse gas (emissions)
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
CRS	Catholic Relief Services
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
PSA	Pam Steele Associates
WORM	Waste in humanitarian Operations: Reduction and Minimization

TABLE OF CONTENT

LIST OF ACRONYMS	3
LIST OF FIGURES	5
BACKGROUND ABOUT WORM	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
NON-TECHNICAL SUMMARY	6
1. INTRODUCTION	7
2. METHOD AND DATA COLLECTION	7
2.1. DEVELOPING CAUSAL LOOP DIAGRAMS (CLDs)	7
2.2. INTEGRATING LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT (LCA) RESULTS	9
2.3. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT	9
3. CLD FOR BBM	9
3.1. VARIABLE DEFINITIONS	10
3.2. FULL MODEL	13
3.3. MARKET ADOPTION AND CONSUMER AWARENESS AND PREFERENCES	13
3.4. ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY PRESSURE: GHG EMISSIONS AND WASTE	15
3.5. SOCIAL POLICY PRESSURE	17
3.6. TECHNICAL PERFORMANCE AND QUALITY	18
3.7. NEGATIVE LAND USE CHANGE, DEFORESTATION, AND BIODIVERSITY LOSS	19
3.8. FOOD INSECURITY	20
3.9. WASTE MANAGEMENT AND CIRCULARITY	22
3.10. SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS FOR WASTE PICKERS	23
3.11. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF PRODUCTION AND WASTE MANAGEMENT BBM vs. FBM	24
4. TRADE-OFFS	25
5. MITIGATION STRATEGIES	27
6. IMPACT ON HUMANITARIAN SECTOR	28
7. CONCLUSIONS	28
REFERENCES	29

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 CLD illustrating the system related to the use of BBM, including environmental, technical, policy and social feedback loops..... 13

Figure 2 CLD of the market adoption and consumer awareness of BBM. Two reinforcing feedback loops are emphasized (R1 and R2). 14

Figure 3 CLD of the policy pressure driven by environmental and waste challenges driven by environmental and waste challenges. Two balancing feedback loops are emphasized (B1 and B2). 16

Figure 4 CLD of the social policy pressure for BBM. Two reinforcing feedback loops are emphasized (R2 and R3). 17

Figure 5 CLD of the technical performance and quality of BBM. Three reinforcing feedback loops are emphasized (R4, R5, and R6). 18

Figure 6 CLD related to potential negative land use change, deforestation, and biodiversity loss as a result of increased BBM. Two reinforcing feedback loops are emphasized (R7 and R8). 20

Figure 7 CLD related to potential food insecurity as a result of increased BBM. Two reinforcing feedback loops (R9 and R10) and one balancing feedback loop (B3) are emphasized 21

Figure 8 CLD related to circularity and waste management as a result of increased BBM. One reinforcing feedback loop (R4) and two balancing feedback loop (B3 and B4) are emphasized. 22

Figure 9 CLD related to sustainable livelihoods of waste pickers as a result of increased BBM. One reinforcing feedback loop (R8) is emphasized. 24

Figure 10 CLD related to the environmental impacts resulting from production and waste management of BBM vs. FBM..... 25

BACKGROUND ABOUT WORM

WORM aims to design guidelines and support actions for circular economy in the humanitarian sector. It integrates bio-based technological solutions, leverages procurement for waste reduction, improves waste management methods and prioritises the sustainable livelihoods of waste pickers. WORM focuses on two selected settings: field hospital deployments and humanitarian livelihood programmes with a waste picking component. Following a collaborative and multi-actor approach, WORM brings together medical and humanitarian organisations, procurement service providers, logistics providers, waste management services and academic partners.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the WORM Project, funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101135392.

The aim of this document (D6.1) is to identify limitations for bio-based solutions. Using Causal Loop Diagrams (CLDs) integrated with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) data, stakeholder engagement, and a literature review, the study explores the dynamic interactions, trade-offs, and unintended consequences of BBM adoption, also in comparison to fossil-based materials (FBM). Additionally, WORM also describes potential mitigation strategies to reduce the unintended consequences and reflects on these opportunities and challenges within the humanitarian sector, especially in medical (e.g., field hospital) settings.

Key findings highlight that BBMs offer environmental benefits such as reduced greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and lower fossil resource use. However, they also pose challenges including competition with food crops, contribution to deforestation, reduced durability and hygiene performance, and potential disruption to waste management systems—particularly affecting informal waste pickers. The CLDs also reveal critical feedback loops across market dynamics, policy pressures, technical performance, environmental impacts, and social outcomes. The report emphasizes the importance of infrastructure, policy support, and material design in enabling circularity and minimizing negative impacts.

To address these challenges, the report proposes mitigation strategies such as promoting bio-based materials that do not compete with food production (e.g., algae, 2nd or 3rd generation biomass), supporting regenerative agriculture, improving waste infrastructure, enhancing product design for circularity, and aligning procurement with life cycle thinking. Stakeholder collaboration is essential to ensure BBM adoption supports both environmental sustainability and social equity.

NON-TECHNICAL SUMMARY

This document looks at the pros and cons of using BBMs, especially as an alternative to FBMs. BBMs can be better for the environment, but they also come with challenges like competing with food crops, potentially causing deforestation, and being harder to recycle. These issues can affect informal waste pickers and areas with poor waste infrastructure. The study also explores how BBMs interact with environmental, social, and policy factors, and suggests ways to reduce negative effects. It highlights the need for better design, strong policies, and teamwork to make BBMs both sustainable and fair.

1. INTRODUCTION

The search for sustainable material alternatives has gained momentum in response to growing concerns over climate change, environmental degradation, and the unsustainable extraction of fossil and mineral resources. Bio-based materials (BBM), often derived from renewable biological sources such as starch, cellulose, or algae, are increasingly explored to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, lower resource consumption, and support circular economy transitions. These materials are often positioned as alternatives to fossil-based materials (FBM), particularly in sectors where materials (e.g., single-use plastic products and packaging) contribute significantly to environmental burdens.

Despite their potential, BBMs present a complex set of trade-offs and systemic challenges. Their production can compete with food crops for land and water, raising concerns about food security and deforestation. In technical applications, especially in health and emergency response contexts, BBMs must meet stringent requirements for durability, hygiene, and safety—criteria that are not always compatible with biodegradability. Moreover, the shift toward compostable or non-recyclable materials may disrupt existing waste management systems and affect the livelihoods of informal waste pickers who rely on recyclable plastics for income.

This deliverable—Task 6.1 of the WORM project—applies a systems-thinking approach to examine the broader system surrounding the use of BBM. Using Causal Loop Diagrams (CLDs), developed in conjunction with Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) from Task 1.2 and informed by stakeholder engagement, we explore the dynamic interactions, feedback loops, and potential unintended consequences of BBM adoption. While the analysis is grounded in a general systems perspective, it also considers specific contexts where material choices are particularly consequential, including humanitarian operations, medical field settings, and sustainable livelihood initiatives for waste pickers.

The following sections describe the methodology and data used to develop CLDs, including the integration of LCA data and stakeholder insights. We then present the system map (i.e., main CLD diagram) and then the key feedback loops related to market dynamics, policy pressure, technical performance, environmental impacts, and sustainable livelihoods for waste pickers. This is followed by a discussion of critical trade-offs and challenges, such as those involving biodegradability, hygiene, food security, and waste management. Building on these insights, we propose mitigation strategies and policy recommendations to support the responsible and context-sensitive adoption of BBM. Additionally, we describe the insights from the CLDs within the context of the humanitarian sector and finalize this deliverable with a conclusions section.

2. METHOD AND DATA COLLECTION

To evaluate the opportunities, trade-offs, and limitations of BBM—also considering humanitarian contexts, medical settings such as field hospitals, and sustainable livelihood initiatives for waste pickers (key components of the WORM project)—Task 6.1 applies a systems-thinking approach using CLDs. This methodology helps uncover complex interdependencies, feedback loops, and potential unintended consequences associated with the adoption of BBM. The following sections outline the methodological framework and data collection process used to develop the CLDs, incorporating insights from LCAs (Task 1.2) and engagement with both internal and external stakeholders.

2.1. DEVELOPING CAUSAL LOOP DIAGRAMS (CLDs)

What is a CLD?

CLDs are qualitative tools used to map relationships between system variables and understand dynamic behaviour (i.e., how changes in one variable influence others, and the system as a whole). Unlike linear

models, CLDs emphasizes circular causality, which allows one to see the “big picture and the interconnected nature of systems” (Barbrook-Johnson and Penn, 2022).

Key elements of a CLD

- **Nodes:** Variables in the system (e.g., greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions or policy support)
- **Arrows:** Arrows indicating causal relationships between variables with the following signs (+ / -):
 - "+" means a change in one variable causes a change in the same direction.
 - "-" means a change in one variable causes a change in the opposite direction.
- **Feedback loops:** Loops which illustrates how a change in one variable affects another, which then influences the original variable
 - Reinforcing Loop (R): Amplifies change, leading to exponential growth or decline.
 - Balancing Loop (B): Resists change, promoting stability or equilibrium.

Approach

To develop the CLD in this deliverable, we followed a structured process based on the methodology described by Barbrook-Johnson & Penn (2022), which includes the following steps:

1. **Collecting data and evidence:** Initial data was gathered from multiple sources, primarily previous WORM deliverables—especially D1.2, along with qualitative insights from D1.1, D1.4, and D4.1. This was supplemented by a review of relevant scientific literature, interviews with external experts (e.g., bio-based experts and manufacturers) and input from project partners (ACF, CRS, ICRC, PSA), who provided operational insights on material requirements in field settings and practical challenges related to biodegradability, hygiene, and durability. For simplicity and clarity, literature review findings are cited and discussed within the descriptions and rationale for the smaller CLDs presented below.
2. **Screening data for variables and connections:** Based on findings from previous WORM deliverables and the literature review, we identified key system variables (e.g., production of BBM, policy support for BBM, GHG emissions) and mapped potential relationships between them (e.g., BBM production requires energy, which increases GHG emissions). Where needed, variables were separated to improve precision—for example, policy pressure was divided into environmental-, waste-, and social-related categories.
3. **Hypothesizing the structure:** The goal of this step was to identify the “core system engine” of the CLD, which may take the form of a central defining variable or a set of key variables and feedback loops that drive system behaviour. We applied a mixed approach, placing “use of BBM” at the centre of the system. This central variable is directly and indirectly influenced by several critical feedback loops, including market adoption and consumer awareness, policy pressure, technical performance, environmental impacts, and waste management and circularity. Additionally, we integrated factors relevant to this deliverable, such as the impact on sustainable livelihoods for waste pickers.
4. **Developing initial diagrams:** In this step, we developed the initial CLD addressing ambiguities and naming key feedback loops. This process involved refining variable definitions and ensuring clarity in causal relationships. We also revisited the literature to support specific topics relevant to the system, such as the relationship between BBM and food security or comparative assessments of technical performance between BBM and FBM. These targeted reviews helped strengthen the rationale behind the feedback loops and informed the structure of the CLDs.
5. **Verifying and amending:** To ensure the model accurately reflects real-world conditions, we used a participatory approach involving both internal partners and external stakeholders to validate the CLDs. This included an external validation workshop with bio-based experts and

manufacturers. Details of this engagement process are provided in Section 2.3: Stakeholder Engagement. Based on feedback from the validation workshop, we added several variables (e.g., the use of regenerative crops to reduce negative land use change).

6. **Analyzing results:** In the final step, we analysed the CLDs to generate insights and recommendations presented in this deliverable. This includes identifying trade-offs, opportunities, and mitigation strategies to address potential unintended consequences of BBM, with particular attention to the humanitarian context. This is further discussed in Section 6: BBM in the humanitarian context.

2.2. INTEGRATING LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT (LCA) RESULTS

The LCAs conducted in Task 1.2 quantified the environmental impacts of producing and disposing (e.g., incineration, landfill, open dump, and open burn) BBM (e.g., maize-based plastics) compared to FBM (e.g., polyvinylchloride). These assessments covered key indicators such as GHG emissions, water ecotoxicity and eutrophication, fossil and mineral resource consumption, and particulate matter generation. For more detailed information on the data collection process for the LCA, please refer to D1.2. WORM integrates these LCA findings into the development of CLDs, using them as a foundation to illustrate and compare the environmental impacts and degradation pathways of BBM versus FBM. It is also important to note that while the LCA results are based on several types of BBM and FBM, they may not fully represent all possible scenarios. This limitation is discussed in Deliverable 1.2 and further addressed in the sections below, where smaller CLDs explore more specific material comparisons and contextual factors.

2.3. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

To ensure the relevance and accuracy of the analysis, the WORM engaged with key internal humanitarian actors—ACF, CRS, ICRC, and PSA—as well as external experts (e.g., bio-based manufacturers) through interviews and workshops. This includes;

1. **Internal workshop with project partners:** An initial brainstorming exercise was held during the WORM General Assembly meeting in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam (October 2024), involving all project partners. The aim was to identify potential trade-offs and mitigation strategies related to BBM, particularly within the humanitarian context.
2. **External validation workshop with bio-based experts:** A validation workshop with bio-based experts and manufacturers was held in September 2025 to gather feedback on the initial CLD and validate the model. During the session, we presented the draft diagram and asked participants to respond via Miro to the following questions: (1) Does this reflect the real-world dynamics you have observed or experienced? (2) Are there important variables or relationships missing? (3) What changes could improve the system's outcomes?
3. **Interviews:** In addition to internal and external workshops, we also incorporated data gathered through targeted interviews. These included discussions with bio-based material manufacturers—conducted as part of the LCA data collection for D1.2—and consultations with waste management experts, which informed D6.1 and 6.2. These interviews provided practical insights into production processes, material performance, and end-of-life challenges, helping to ground the CLD in operational realities.

3. CLD FOR BBM

In the following sections we define the variables and present the full CLD related to the use of BBM. This is followed by a presentation and discussion of different feedback loops and sections of the larger CLD

which focus on the following areas: (1) market adoption and consumer awareness and preference; (2) environmental- and waste-related policy pressure; (3) social-related policy pressure; (4) technical performance and quality; (5) negative land use change, deforestation, and loss of biodiversity; (6) food insecurity; (7) waste management and circularity; (8) sustainable livelihoods for waste pickers; (9) environmental impacts of producing and disposing BBM compared to FBM.

3.1. VARIABLE DEFINITIONS

- **2nd or 3rd gen. biomass:** Advanced biomass sources that do not compete directly with food crops, such as agricultural residues or dedicated energy crops.
- **Algae-BBM:** BBM derived from algae, offering renewable and potentially non-land-intensive alternatives.
- **Availability of food and feed products for consumption:** Food and feed products are accessible for human consumption either directly (e.g., tomatoes) or indirectly (e.g., feed for livestock that will later be consumed by humans).
- **BBM biodegradable innovation:** Technological advancements that enhance the biodegradability of BBM.
- **BBM production:** The manufacturing of BBM.
- **BBM production fossil and mineral resource use:** The extent to which BBM production relies on fossil and mineral resources.
- **BBM production GHG emissions:** GHG emissions resulting from the production of BBM.
- **BBM raw materials price:** The cost of raw materials used in the production of BBM.
- **BBM recycling innovation:** Technological advancements that improve the recyclability of BBM.
- **BBM technology innovation:** Innovations in technology that enhance the performance, sustainability, or cost-effectiveness of BBM.
- **BBM WM GHG and PM emissions:** GHG and particulate matter (PM) emissions from waste management of BBM.
- **Bio-based additives:** Additives derived from biological sources used to enhance the properties of BBM.
- **Biodegradable BBM:** BBM that can decompose naturally through biological processes.
- **Biodiversity loss:** Reduction in the variety of life forms due to environmental degradation or land use changes.
- **Consumer awareness and preference to buy:** The level of consumer knowledge and inclination to purchase BBM.
- **Deforestation:** The clearing of forests, often for agriculture or development, impacting ecosystems and carbon storage.
- **Demand for BBM:** The market need or desire for BBM.
- **Disposed waste (e.g., landfill, incineration):** Waste that is discarded through destructive methods (e.g., landfill or incineration).
- **Energy use:** The amount of energy consumed in the production of BBM and FBM.
- **Environmental degradation:** The deterioration of the environment.
- **Environmental policy pressure:** Pressure related to environmental awareness or concerns (e.g., climate change) on policy.
- **FBM production:** The manufacturing of FBM.
- **FBM production fossil and mineral resource use:** The extent to which FBM production relies on fossil and mineral resources.
- **FBM production GHG emissions:** GHG emissions resulting from the production of FBM.

- **FBM WM GHG and PM emissions:** GHG and PM emissions from waste management of FBM.
- **Food and feed crop production:** The cultivation of crops intended for human consumption and animal feed.
- **Food security:** The state of having reliable access to sufficient and nutritious food.
- **Government incentives:** Financial or policy-based support provided by governments to promote BBM.
- **Government policy support:** Governmental backing for BBM through regulations, funding, or strategic initiatives.
- **Government standards:** Regulatory benchmarks set by governments to ensure quality and safety of BBM.
- **Greenhouse gas emissions:** Emissions of gases that contribute to global warming and climate change
- **Improved sterilization compatibility BBM:** Enhancements in BBM that allow better compatibility with sterilization processes.
- **Investment in BBM technology:** Financial resources allocated to the development and improvement of BBM technologies.
- **Lack of infrastructure to biodegrade BBM:** Insufficient facilities or systems to support the biodegradation of BBM.
- **Lack of infrastructure to recycle:** Insufficient facilities or systems to support the recycling of materials.
- **Land use for BBM:** The allocation of land resources for the cultivation or production of BBM.
- **Land use for food and feed crops:** The allocation of land resources for growing food and feed crops.
- **Market dialogue:** Communication and engagement among stakeholders in the BBM market.
- **Market price for BBM:** The selling price of BBM in the market.
- **Materials for waste pickers:** Materials accessible for people who collect waste with the intention to sell in the informal sector.
- **Negative land use change:** Land use changes that result in environmental harm, such as deforestation.
- **Non-land based BBM:** BBM produced without the use of land resources.
- **Non-land competitive BBM:** BBM that does not compete with land needed for food or feed production.
- **Policy pressure:** Influence from policies that drive changes in production or consumption practices.
- **Production cost for BBM:** The total cost incurred in producing BBM.
- **Ratio of BBM to FBM hygiene performance:** Comparison of hygiene performance between BBM and FBM.
- **Ratio of BBM to FBM mechanical durability:** Comparison of mechanical durability between BBM and FBM.
- **Ratio of BBM to FBM WM GHG and PM emissions:** Comparison of waste management GHG and PM emissions between BBM and FBM.
- **Ratio of production BBM to FBM GHG emissions and resource use:** Comparison of production GHG emissions and resource use between BBM and FBM.
- **Raw material production for BBM:** The process of generating raw materials used in BBM production.
- **Recyclable BBM:** BBM that can be processed and reused through recycling.
- **Recyclable FBM:** FBM that can be processed and reused through recycling.
- **Recycled waste:** Waste materials that have been processed for reuse.

- **Reduced hygiene performance compared to FBM:** Lower hygiene effectiveness of BBM relative to FBM.
- **Reduced mechanical durability compared to FBM:** Lower mechanical strength of BBM relative to FBM.
- **Reduced production GHG emissions and resource use compared to FBM:** Lower GHG emissions and fossil and mineral resource use to produce BBM compared to FBM.
- **Reduced WM GHG and PM emissions compared to FBM:** Lower waste management GHG and PM emissions of BBM compared to FBM.
- **Regenerative crops:** Crops that restore soil health and biodiversity while being cultivated, mitigating negative land use change.
- **Regulatory barriers:** Obstacles created by regulations that hinder BBM development or adoption.
- **Regulatory complexity:** The degree of intricacy in regulatory frameworks affecting BBM.
- **Regulatory uncertainty:** Unpredictability in regulations that may affect BBM investment or adoption.
- **Research and development:** Activities aimed at innovating and improving BBM technologies.
- **Sales BBM:** The volume or value of BBM sold in the market.
- **Shorter life span of BBM:** The reduced durability or longevity of BBM compared to alternatives (e.g., FBM).
- **Social-related policy pressure:** Public-driven policy influence promoting sustainable practices.
- **Subsidies:** Financial support provided to reduce the cost of BBM production or adoption.
- **Sustainable livelihoods waste pickers:** Economic opportunities for waste pickers through sustainable waste practices.
- **Synthetic fertilizer and pesticide use:** Application of chemical inputs in agriculture affecting BBM raw materials.
- **Taxes and tariffs:** Government-imposed financial charges affecting BBM market prices.
- **Technical performance BBM compared to FBM:** Overall performance of BBM relative to FBM.
- **Trade barriers:** Restrictions on international trade that affect BBM supply chains.
- **Use of BBM:** The extent to which BBM are utilized.
- **Use of FBM:** The extent to which FBM are utilized.
- **Waste BBM:** Discarded BBM after use.
- **Waste FBM:** Discarded FBM after use.
- **Waste picker income:** Earnings generated by informal waste pickers collecting and selling waste materials.
- **Waste related policy pressure:** Policy pressure due to challenges related to waste.
- **Waste sold by waste pickers:** Materials collected and sold by waste pickers.
- **Waste sorted:** The process of separating waste into categories for recycling or disposal.
- **Water ecotoxicity and eutrophication:** Environmental harm caused by nutrient pollution and toxic substances in water bodies.
- **Willingness- to-pay:** Consumer readiness to spend money on BBM products.

Figure 2 CLD of the market adoption and consumer awareness of BBM. Two reinforcing feedback loops are emphasized (R1 and R2).

Causality for market adoption and consumer awareness and preference

- Rising **demand for BBM** stimulates increased **BBM production**, boosts **sales**, and attracts greater **investment in BBM technologies** (Filho *et al.*, 2022; Velasquez *et al.*, 2025; Weinrich and Herbes, 2023).
- **Investment** fosters **innovation**, which in turn reduces **BBM production costs**, potentially lowering **market prices** and further increasing **sales**, and subsequently **use of BBM** (Filho *et al.*, 2022).
- **Use of BBM** increases **consumer awareness and preference to buy**, which in turn drives further **BBM demand** (Ruf *et al.*, 2022; Velasquez *et al.*, 2025).
- **Consumer awareness and preference to buy** is driven by both **market dialogue** and **willingness-to-pay for BBM** (Filho *et al.*, 2022; Ruf *et al.*, 2022).
- The cost of **BBM production** is influenced by the **price of raw materials**—higher input costs lead to higher **production** expenses (Salazar Sandoval *et al.*, 2024; Wellenreuther *et al.*, 2021).
- **Subsidies** and **government incentives** reduce **BBM production costs**, which can lower **market prices** and boost adoption (Saddler *et al.*, 2020; Sharma *et al.*, 2020; Wang *et al.*, 2021).
- Conversely, **taxes, tariffs, and trade barriers** may increase **costs**, raising prices and slowing market uptake (Pal, 2025).
- **Regulatory uncertainty** and **complexity** can also hinder investment and innovation, keeping production costs—and prices—high (Fabrizio, 2013).

Loops

R1: Demand for BBM →+ Investment in BBM technology →+ BBM technology innovation →- Production cost for BBM →+ Market price for BBM →- Sales of BBM →+ Use of BBM →+ Consumer awareness and preference to buy →+ Demand for BBM

Rising demand boosts investment, drives innovation, lowers production costs and market prices, increases sales, use, and awareness, which leads to more demand to describe market adoption and development in a **reinforcing feedback loop**.

R2: Increased consumer awareness and preference to buy →+ Demand for BBM →+ Sales of BBM →+ Use of BBM →+ Consumer awareness and preference to buy

Increased consumer awareness and preference to buy drives demand, which in turn increases sales, use, and then awareness in a **reinforcing feedback loop**.

3.4. ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY PRESSURE: GHG EMISSIONS AND WASTE

Figure 3 shows how environmental and waste-related challenges generate policy pressure that influences the adoption of BBM. Environmental and waste-related policy pressure refers to the influence exerted by environmental challenges—such as rising GHG emissions and increasing volumes of waste—on government decision-making and regulatory action. This pressure often leads to the development of policies, standards, and incentives aimed at reducing environmental harm, promoting sustainable practices, reducing waste, and encouraging the adoption of cleaner technologies and materials.

Figure 3 CLD of the policy pressure driven by environmental and waste challenges driven by environmental and waste challenges. Two balancing feedback loops are emphasized (B1 and B2).

Causality for environmental- and waste-related policy pressure

- Increased **use of FBM** leads to greater generation of **FBM waste**, which contributes to **waste-related policy pressure, environmental policy pressure**, and broader **policy** responses (UNOSD, 2024).
- Similarly, rising **GHG emissions** drive **environmental degradation**, which intensifies **environmental policy pressure**, and contributes to broader **policy** pressure momentum (Meerab K, 2023).
- The increased **use of BBM** helps reduce **production-related GHG emissions and resource use compared to FBM**, while also decreasing overall reliance on **FBM. (LCA results)** (Velasquez *et al.*, 2025; Weiss *et al.*, 2012; Zuiderveen *et al.*, 2023)
- As **policy pressure** builds, **government policy support** strengthens, leading to the development of more **government standards and incentives**, which in turn stimulate further **research and development** (Ao, 2025).
- **Government incentives** also expand **subsidies for BBM**, boosting both **market demand and sales** (Wang *et al.*, 2021).

Loops

B1: Use of FBM →+ Waste FBM →+ Waste related policy pressure →+ Environmental policy pressure →+ Policy pressure →+ Government policy support →+ Government standards →- Regulatory barriers →- Sales BBM →+ Use of BBM →- Use of FBM

Greater use of FBM leads to more FBM waste, which increases waste-related and environmental policy pressure. This drives broader policy pressure, prompting stronger government support and standards. As

regulatory barriers fall, BBM sales rise, encouraging its use and ultimately reducing reliance on FBM in a **balancing feedback loop**.

B2: Use of BBM →+ Reduced production of GHG emissions and resources use compared to FBM →- GHG emissions →+ Environmental degradation →+ Environmental policy pressure →+ Policy pressure →+ Government policy support →+ Government standards →- Regulatory barriers →- Sales BBM →+ Use of BBM

Increased BBM use reduces GHG emissions and resource use, environmental harm, and thus policy pressure. As pressure eases, the urgency to remove regulatory barriers declines, which can slow further BBM adoption. This creates a **balancing feedback loop** where environmental gains reduce the drivers for continued policy support, stabilizing BBM growth.

3.5. SOCIAL POLICY PRESSURE

Figure 4 shows the relationship between social-related policy pressure and BBM. Social policy pressure refers to the influence of societal values, public opinion, and consumer behaviour on the development of policies and regulations. It arises from growing awareness, dialogue, and demand for socially responsible products and practices, prompting governments and institutions to respond with supportive measures such as incentives, subsidies, and standards that align with public expectations and social priorities.

Figure 4 CLD of the social policy pressure for BBM. Two reinforcing feedback loops are emphasized (R2 and R3).

Causality for social-related policy pressure

- Increased **market dialogue** and **willingness-to-pay** enhances **consumer awareness and preference to buy** (Filho *et al.*, 2022; Ruf *et al.*, 2022).

Loops

R3: Consumer awareness and preference to buy →+ Social related policy pressure →+ Policy pressure →+ Government policy support →+ Government incentives →+ Subsidies →+ Sales BBM →+ Use of BBM →+ Consumer awareness and preference to buy

Increased consumer awareness drives social related policy pressure, leading to broader policy support, incentives, subsidies, and increased BBM adoption in a **reinforcing feedback loop**

(R2 described in Section 3.3)

3.6. TECHNICAL PERFORMANCE AND QUALITY

Figure 5 describes technical performance and quality of BBM in comparison to FBM. Here, technical performance and quality refer to the functional characteristics and reliability of BBM products, including their mechanical durability, hygiene compatibility, and overall suitability for intended applications, which are key factors for the use of BBM in (humanitarian) medical settings. These attributes are shaped by material composition, technological innovation, and the integration of additives, and they play a critical role in determining the competitiveness of BBM compared to conventional alternatives like FBM.

Figure 5 CLD of the technical performance and quality of BBM. Three reinforcing feedback loops are emphasized (R4, R5, and R6).

Causality for technical performance and quality

- Rising **demand for BBM** drives increased **investment in BBM technology**, which accelerates **BBM innovation** and promotes the development of **bio-based additives** (Filho *et al.*, 2022).
- **Bio-based additives** improve both **mechanical durability** and **sterilization compatibility of BBM**, enhancing its **mechanical and hygiene performance relative to FBM** and contributing to **improved overall technical performance** (Castro-Dominguez *et al.*, 2025; Kumari *et al.*, 2023).
- However, the use of BBM in its current form may **reduce hygiene performance and mechanical durability compared to FBM**, potentially hindering adoption unless further technical improvements are achieved (Chang *et al.*, 2020; Kumari *et al.*, 2023).
- The inclusion of **bio-based additives** can also complicate BBM composition, reducing its potential for **recycling and biodegradability** due to increased ingredient complexity (Chang *et al.*, 2020).
- Lower **mechanical durability of BBM compared to FBM** contributes to a **shorter lifespan**, which may affect its competitiveness in long-term applications (Chang *et al.*, 2020).

Loops

R4: Biodegradable BBM →- Recyclable BBM →- Biodegradable BBM

More biodegradable BBM reduces recyclability, while more recyclable BBM limits biodegradability in a **reinforcing feedback loop**.

R5: Government standards →+ Research and development →+ BBM technology innovation →+ Technical performance of BBM compared to FBM →+ Government standards

Government standards stimulate research and development, which drives innovation in BBM technology. This innovation enhances the technical performance of BBM compared to FBM, which further strengthens and refines government standards in support of BBM advancement in a **reinforcing feedback loop**.

R6: Government standards →+ Technical performance of BBM compared to FBM →+ Government standards

Improved government standards enhance BBM's technical performance relative to FBM, which in turn reinforces the development of further standards in a **reinforcing feedback loop**.

3.7. NEGATIVE LAND USE CHANGE, DEFORESTATION, AND BIODIVERSITY LOSS

Figure 6 illustrates the dynamics related to negative land use change, deforestation, and biodiversity loss resulting from the use of BBM. Negative land use change refers to the transformation of natural landscapes—such as forests, wetlands, or grasslands—into areas used for industrial, agricultural (as in this case), or commercial purposes, often resulting in environmental harm. Deforestation is a major consequence of such changes, contributing to GHG emissions and the loss of critical ecosystems. Biodiversity loss occurs when species and habitats are disrupted or destroyed, reducing ecological resilience and accelerating environmental degradation.

Figure 6 CLD related to potential negative land use change, deforestation, and biodiversity loss as a result of increased BBM. Two reinforcing feedback loops are emphasized (R7 and R8).

Causality for negative land use change, deforestation, and loss of biodiversity

- **Raw material production for BBM** increases **land use for BBM**, leading to **negative land use change** (Weiss *et al.*, 2012).
- **Regenerative crops** help mitigate **negative land use change** (Vejendla *et al.*, 2025; Villat and Nicholas, 2023).
- **Negative land use changes** contribute to **deforestation**, which generates **GHG emissions** and accelerates **environmental degradation** (Lawrence *et al.*, 2022; Li *et al.*, 2024).
- **Deforestation** also leads to **biodiversity loss**, compounding **environmental degradation** (Lawrence *et al.*, 2022).

Loops

R9: Biodiversity loss →+ Environmental degradation →+ Biodiversity loss

Biodiversity loss worsens environmental degradation, which in turn accelerates further biodiversity loss in a **reinforcing feedback loop**.

R8: Deforestation →+ Negative land use change →+ Deforestation

Deforestation increases negative land use change, which in turn further drives deforestation, forming a **reinforcing feedback loop**.

3.8. FOOD INSECURITY

Figure 7 describes the complexities associated with food insecurity and the use of BBM. Food insecurity refers to the condition in which people lack reliable access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food to meet their dietary needs. In the context of BBM production, food insecurity can arise when agricultural resources—such as land, water, and inputs—are diverted from food and feed crop cultivation toward

biomass production, potentially impacting food availability, affordability, and environmental sustainability.

Figure 7 CLD related to potential food insecurity as a result of increased BBM. Two reinforcing feedback loops (R9 and R10) and one balancing feedback loop (B3) are emphasized

Causality for food insecurity:

- Increased **raw material production for BBM** drives higher **synthetic fertilizer and pesticide use**, which leads to greater **water ecotoxicity and eutrophication**, worsening **environmental degradation** and ultimately reducing **food security** (Weiss *et al.*, 2012; Zuiderveen *et al.*, 2023).
- **Synthetic fertilizer and pesticide** use also increases the **availability of food and feed products for consumption** in the short term (Penuelas *et al.*, 2023).
- Greater **food and feed crop production** boosts the **availability of food and feed products for consumption**, which in turn enhances **food security**.
- Food and feed crop production also contributes to the generation of 2nd or 3rd generation biomass (Lee and Lavoie, 2013; Zuiderveen *et al.*, 2023).
- **Non-land competitive BBM**—including **algae, non-land based BBM, and 2nd or 3rd generation biomass**—reduces the need for **land use for BBM** (Akchaya *et al.*, 2025; Lee and Lavoie, 2013; Singh *et al.*, 2022; Zuiderveen *et al.*, 2023).

Loops

R9: Food and feed crop production →+ 2nd or 3rd generation biomass →+ Non-land competitive BBM →- Land use for BBM →- Land use for food and feed crops →+ Food and feed crop production

Food and feed crop production supports the development of 2nd or 3rd generation biomass, which promotes non-land competitive BBM. This reduces land use for BBM, easing pressure on land for food and feed crops, and ultimately increasing food and feed crop production in a **reinforcing feedback loop**.

Causality for circularity and waste management of BBM:

- Advancements in **BBM technology** are driving **innovation in biodegradable BBM, BBM recycling, and bio-based additives** (Velasquez *et al.*, 2025).
- Increased **innovation in BBM recycling** supports the development of more **recyclable BBM**, while advancements in **BBM biodegradability** lead to more **biodegradable BBM**. However, the potential to recycle or biodegrade BBM is limited by inadequate **infrastructure** (Velasquez *et al.*, 2025).
- The **lack of infrastructure for BBM recycling and biodegradation** results in more BBM being **disposed of via landfill or incineration** (Serrano-Aguirre and Prieto, 2024; Wu *et al.*, 2024).
- Additionally, the use of **bio-based additives** can reduce the **recyclability and biodegradability of BBM**, as previously noted (Castro-Dominguez *et al.*, 2025; Chang *et al.*, 2020; Jha *et al.*, 2024; Velasquez *et al.*, 2025).
- The **use of BBM** contributes to the generation of **waste BBM**, which increases the volume of waste requiring **disposal** (e.g., landfill, incineration), while also increasing the amount of **recyclable and biodegradable BBM**. At the same time, it reduces the need for **raw material production for BBM** (Zaborowska and Bernat, 2023).
- The more **biodegradable BBM**, the less **recyclable BBM**, and vice versa.

Loops

B4: Waste BBM →+ Recyclable BBM →- Raw material for production of BBM →+ Waste BBM

Increased waste BBM boosts recyclable BBM, which reduces raw material demand for BBM production, but ultimately contributes to more waste BBM generation in a **balancing feedback loop**.

(R4 and B4 described above in Sections 3.6 and 3.8 respectively)

3.10. SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS FOR WASTE PICKERS

Figure 9 illustrates the relationship between the increased use of BBM and sustainable livelihoods for waste pickers. In general, sustainable livelihoods for waste pickers refer to stable and dignified income-generating opportunities within the informal waste sector, supported by access to recyclable materials, fair market conditions, and safe working environments. In the context of BBM, the availability and type of waste—particularly recyclable BBM—can significantly influence the ability of waste pickers to earn a living, making material design and waste management practices critical to their economic and social well-being. The CLD below is based on discussions with experts in the informal waste sector.

Figure 9 CLD related to sustainable livelihoods of waste pickers as a result of increased BBM. One reinforcing feedback loop (R4) is emphasized.

Causality for sustainable livelihoods for waste pickers related to BBM:

- Increased **use of BBM** results in greater production of **waste BBM**, which includes **recyclable** (providing **materials for waste pickers**), **biodegradable**, and general waste for **disposal**. This shift also leads to a reduction in the **use of FBM**.
- Similarly, increased **use of FBM** generates **waste FBM**, which can either be **recycled**—providing more **materials for waste pickers**—or disposed of, contributing to **environmental degradation** through methods such as incineration or landfill.
- A higher proportion of **biodegradable BBM** reduces the total volume of recyclable **materials available to waste pickers**, whereas more **recyclable BBM** increases the supply of materials they can collect.
- Greater availability of **recyclable materials enables waste pickers to sort and sell more waste**, thereby enhancing their **income** and promoting **sustainable livelihoods** within the informal waste sector.

(R4 described above in Section 3.6)

3.11. ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF PRODUCTION AND WASTE MANAGEMENT BBM vs. FBM

Lastly, Figure 10 illustrates the generation of environmental impacts comparing the production and waste management of BBM vs. FBM based on the LCA results. Environmental impacts of production and waste management refer to the effects that manufacturing and disposal processes have on natural resources, ecosystems, and climate. In comparing BBM and FBM, these impacts include GHG emissions, energy use, resource consumption, freshwater ecotoxicity and eutrophication, generated during production as well

as GHG emissions and particulate matter (PM) from waste treatment methods such as incineration or landfill. The basis of this CLD are generated from the LCA in T1.2.

Figure 10 CLD related to the environmental impacts resulting from production and waste management of BBM vs. FBM.

Causality for environmental impacts of production and waste management related to BBM compared to FBM:

- The **production of both BBM and FBM** contributes to **GHG emissions** and **resource consumption**, including **energy use**, which indirectly increases total GHG emissions.
- However, **BBM production** generally requires fewer **fossil and mineral resources** and results in lower **GHG emissions** compared to FBM. As **the ratio of BBM to FBM** increases, overall **resource use and emissions** decrease—while a higher reliance on FBM leads to greater environmental impact.
- This shift toward **BBM production** therefore contributes to reduced **GHG emissions and resource depletion**, helping mitigate environmental degradation.
- Nonetheless, BBM’s **shorter lifespan** compared to FBM may limit these benefits over time.
- Similarly, BBM disposal produces fewer GHG emissions and less particulate matter (PM) than FBM, further reducing the environmental impact of waste management as BBM usage increases.

4. TRADE-OFFS

Transitioning to BBM is often framed as a more sustainable solution. However, it’s clear from the results of the CLDs presented above that there are several important trade-offs to consider. The following

paragraphs describe the major trade-offs identified in this deliverable, especially considering medical and/or challenging contexts.

Biodegradability vs. durability

BBM are often designed to biodegrade and/or typically have a shorter lifespan than FBM. While this biodegradability may reduce long-term environmental harm generated by untreated waste, this very property may also reduce their mechanical strength and durability, causing them to break down quickly, especially under harsh conditions. If BBMs degrade too quickly they may also need frequent replacements, which also increases logistical burdens, costs, and emissions related to transport and production.

Biodegradability vs. hygiene

Another critical tension is between BBM/biodegradable materials and hygiene performance, which may also include reduced sterilization compatibility in comparison to FBM. This is especially relevant in medical contexts (e.g., field hospital settings) where inadequate hygiene may lead to disease outbreaks. The need to revert to conventional materials for safety reasons may create inconsistencies in sustainability goals and complicate procurement strategies.

Technical performance vs. circularity

To reach similar durability and hygiene performance as FBMs, BBM often require the incorporation of biocomposites or additives. While these additives enhance technical functionality, they also complicate material composition, making recycling or biodegradation more difficult. This trade-off can compromise the sustainability of BBMs at their end-of-life stage. Furthermore, increased use of performance-enhancing additives may exacerbate waste management challenges, particularly in regions with limited or inadequate infrastructure to process BBM waste effectively.

BBM vs. food security

Some BBMs are derived from agricultural crops such as maize and sugarcane. Although these raw materials are renewable, their cultivation can compete with food production for essential resources like land, water, and nutrients. In regions already experiencing food insecurity, this competition may intensify existing challenges. Moreover, rising demand for BBMs can drive up the cost of agricultural inputs, potentially impacting the affordability and availability of resources needed for food and animal feed production.

BBM vs. deforestation and climate change

Increasing demand for land to produce BBM can result in adverse land use changes, including deforestation and biodiversity loss. When forests are cleared to cultivate agricultural crops—often in the form of monocultures—the ecological resilience of these areas is diminished. This process also contributes to GHG emissions through land use change. Consequently, such environmental impacts may undermine the very sustainability goals that BBMs are intended to support.

Material substitution vs. livelihoods of waste pickers

Shifting towards biodegradable or non-recyclable BBM can disrupt existing informal waste management systems, particularly those reliant on the collection and resale of recyclable materials. Waste pickers, who depend on the economic value of recyclable waste, may find BBMs less valuable or entirely unsellable. This disruption threatens their livelihoods and reduces their ability to sustain themselves. Additionally, it may undermine the effectiveness of circular economy initiatives by limiting the availability of recyclable inputs and excluding vulnerable groups from waste-based economic activities.

5. MITIGATION STRATEGIES

Addressing the potential trade-offs that can arise from the use of BBM requires a comprehensive approach that considers diverse stakeholder perspectives, including those of consumers, policymakers, and manufacturers. These trade-offs often involve tensions between environmental goals, economic feasibility, and social equity. While various strategies exist to navigate these challenges, the following examples are drawn from insights generated through CLDs.

Promoting low-impact feedstocks

To reduce environmental and social pressures associated with BBM production, it is essential to prioritize feedstocks that do not compete with food crops or contribute to deforestation. This includes non-land-based sources such as algae, agricultural residues, and second- or third-generation biomass. These alternatives help avoid land-use conflicts and minimize biodiversity loss, while still supporting the transition away from FBM. Encouraging the use of these feedstocks through procurement policies and research funding can significantly reduce the negative impacts of BBM scaling.

Supporting regenerative agriculture

BBM production can be aligned with regenerative agricultural practices that restore soil health, improve water retention, reduce negative land-use change, and enhance biodiversity. By incentivizing the cultivation of regenerative crops—such as cover crops or agroforestry systems—governments and organizations can mitigate the environmental degradation often associated with monoculture bio-feedstock farming. These practices also contribute to climate resilience and long-term sustainability, making BBM sourcing more ecologically responsible.

Improving technical performance

One of the key challenges in BBM adoption is ensuring that materials meet the durability and hygiene standards required for specific contexts, e.g., humanitarian and/or medical contexts. To address this, on one side, investment in research and development is needed to enhance BBM mechanical strength, sterilization compatibility, and overall performance. This will lead to innovations in bio-based additives and material engineering can help bridge the gap between biodegradability and functionality, ensuring BBMs are fit for purpose without compromising sustainability goals.

Enhancing waste management infrastructure

Effective waste management systems are critical to realizing the environmental benefits of BBMs. This includes expanding infrastructure for composting and recycling, particularly in regions where BBMs are being introduced. Localized composting facilities, advanced sorting technologies, and public education campaigns can help ensure BBMs are disposed of properly. Without these systems, BBMs may end up in landfills or incinerators, negating their environmental advantages and contributing to pollution. This is especially challenging in areas where humanitarian organizations are active but is an essential step to reduce the environmental impacts at the end-of-life.

Designing for circularity

BBMs should be designed with clear end-of-life pathways in mind. This means choosing formulations that are either recyclable or compostable, depending on the local waste management context. Avoiding complex additives that hinder biodegradability or recyclability is crucial, when possible. Material designers should aim for simplicity and compatibility with existing systems, enabling BBMs to be reintegrated into the production cycle and reducing reliance on virgin resources.

Protecting waste picker livelihoods

In many regions, informal waste pickers rely on recyclable plastics for income. The shift to compostable or non-recyclable BBMs can reduce the value of waste streams and threaten these livelihoods. To mitigate

this, BBMs should be made recyclable where possible, and policies should be inclusive of waste picker communities. This mitigation strategy is especially challenging because the end goal is to reduce total waste that needs to be treated, which essentially leads to less materials for waste pickers.

Aligning procurement with life cycle thinking

Organizations, especially in humanitarian and medical sectors, should adopt life cycle thinking in their procurement decisions. This involves using LCA approaches to evaluate the environmental impacts of materials from production to disposal. By prioritizing BBMs with lower GHG emissions, reduced resource use, and manageable waste impacts, procurement teams can make informed choices that align with sustainability goals.

6. IMPACT ON HUMANITARIAN SECTOR

The adoption of BBM presents both opportunities and challenges for the humanitarian sector, where material choices directly affect operational effectiveness, safety, and overall sustainability. Humanitarian operations often take place in resource-constrained and/or extreme environments that demand durable, hygienic, and logistically efficient materials. While BBMs offer environmental benefits—such as reduced GHG emissions and lower fossil resource use—their biodegradability can compromise mechanical strength and longevity. This is particularly problematic in emergency shelters, field hospitals, and mobile clinics, where materials must withstand harsh conditions and prolonged use. Additionally, BBMs may not meet the stringent hygiene standards required for medical applications, posing risks to public health in vulnerable populations.

From a systems perspective, the shift to BBM also affects supply chains and waste management practices. In regions with limited infrastructure, compostable or non-recyclable BBMs may end up in landfills or open dumps, undermining their environmental advantages. Moreover, the transition to BBM can disrupt informal recycling economies, especially in urban areas where waste pickers rely on recyclable plastics for income. If BBMs are not designed to be recyclable within existing systems, this could reduce the availability of valuable waste materials and threaten livelihoods.

Despite these challenges, BBMs hold promise for the humanitarian sector if adopted thoughtfully. By integrating life cycle thinking into procurement decisions, humanitarian organizations can select BBMs that balance environmental performance with operational needs. Innovations in BBM technology—such as improved sterilization compatibility and enhanced durability—can make these materials more suitable for field use. Furthermore, inclusive policy design and investment in waste infrastructure can ensure that BBM adoption supports both environmental sustainability and social equity. Ultimately, the humanitarian sector has a unique opportunity to lead by example, demonstrating how responsible material transitions can align with broader goals of resilience, dignity, and sustainability.

7. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable has applied a systems-thinking approach using CLDs to explore the complex dynamics surrounding the adoption and impact of BBM in humanitarian and medical contexts. By integrating insights from LCAs and stakeholder engagement, the analysis has revealed key feedback loops that influence market adoption, policy pressure, technical performance, environmental outcomes, and social implications, including considering informal waste pickers, the humanitarian context, and the needs of medical settings.

The findings highlight both the opportunities and trade-offs associated with BBM, including its potential to reduce environmental impacts (e.g., GHG emissions, resource use) compared to FBM, as well as risks related to land use change, biodiversity loss, and food insecurity. The CLDs also underscore the

importance of infrastructure, policy support, and material design in enabling circularity and minimizing unintended consequences.

To support sustainable transitions, the report outlines a set of mitigation strategies that address environmental, social, and technical challenges. These include promoting low-impact feedstocks, enhancing waste management systems, improving product durability, and aligning procurement with life cycle thinking. The role of stakeholders—governments, manufacturers, humanitarian actors, and informal workers—is critical in implementing these measures and ensuring that BBM contributes to both environmental sustainability and social equity. This systems-based analysis provides a foundation for informed decision-making and strategic planning within the WORM project and beyond, supporting the EU's broader goals for sustainable innovation and responsible material transitions.

REFERENCES

- Akchaya, K., Parasuraman, P., Pandian, K., Vijayakumar, S., Thirukumaran, K., Mustaffa, M. R. A. F., Rajpoot, S. K., & Choudhary, A. K. (2025). Boosting resource use efficiency, soil fertility, food security, ecosystem services, and climate resilience with legume intercropping: a review. In *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems* (Vol. 9). Frontiers Media SA. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2025.1527256>
- Ao, S. (2025). The Impact of Government Subsidy Policies on Industrial Innovation. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 13(01), 502–513. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojbm.2025.131028>
- Barbrook-Johnson, P., & Penn, A. S. (2022). Causal Loop Diagrams. In *Systems Mapping How to build and use causal models of systems* (pp. 47–59). Springer Nature Switzerland AG. https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-01919-7_4
- Castro-Dominguez, B., Gröls, J. R., Alkandari, S., Perge, L., Sierra-Avila, C., Ramirez, H. Z., de Lima Fontes, M., Yamada, C., Lazarini, S. C., Silva, J. M., Lustri, W. R., & da Silva Barud, H. (2025). Biopolymers and biocomposites: a comprehensive review of feedstocks, functionalities, and advanced manufacturing techniques for sustainable applications. *Biotechnology for Sustainable Materials*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s44316-025-00029-y>
- Chang, B. P., Mohanty, A. K., & Misra, M. (2020). Studies on durability of sustainable biobased composites: a review. In *RSC Advances* (Vol. 10, Issue 31, pp. 17955–17999). Royal Society of Chemistry. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9ra09554c>
- Fabrizio, K. R. (2013). The effect of regulatory uncertainty on investment: Evidence from renewable energy generation. *Journal of Law, Economics, and Organization*, 29(4), 765–798. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jleo/ews007>
- Filho, W. L., Barbir, J., Abubakar, I. R., Paço, A., Stasiskiene, Z., Hornbogen, M., Fendt, M. T. C., Voronova, V., & Klõga, M. (2022). Consumer attitudes and concerns with bioplastics use: An international study. *PLoS ONE*, 17(4 April). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0266918>
- Jha, S., Akula, B., Enyioma, H., Novak, M., Amin, V., & Liang, H. (2024). Biodegradable Biobased Polymers: A Review of the State of the Art, Challenges, and Future Directions. In *Polymers* (Vol. 16, Issue 16). Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI). <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16162262>
- Kumari, S., Rao, A., Kaur, M., & Dhanial, G. (2023). Petroleum-Based Plastics Versus Bio-Based Plastics: A Review. In *Nature Environment and Pollution Technology* (Vol. 22, Issue 3, pp. 1111–1124). Technoscience Publications. <https://doi.org/10.46488/NEPT.2023.v22i03.003>

- Lawrence, D., Coe, M., Walker, W., Verchot, L., & Vandecar, K. (2022). The Unseen Effects of Deforestation: Biophysical Effects on Climate. *Frontiers in Forests and Global Change*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3389/ffgc.2022.756115>
- Lee, R. A., & Lavoie, J. M. (2013). From first- to third-generation biofuels: Challenges of producing a commodity from a biomass of increasing complexity. *Animal Frontiers*, 3(2), 6–11. <https://doi.org/10.2527/af.2013-0010>
- Li, L., Awada, T., Zhang, Y., & Paustian, K. (2024). Global Land Use Change and Its Impact on Greenhouse Gas Emissions. *Global Change Biology*, 30(12). <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.17604>
- Meerab K. (2023). Addressing the Global Environmental Crisis: A Comprehensive Review of Current Strategies and Challenges. *International Research Journal of Arts and Social Science*, 11(3), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.14303/2276-6502.2023.93>
- Pal, H. (2025). Modeling the dynamic effects of tariffs on economic variables and trade policies. *Future Business Journal*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-025-00507-9>
- Penuelas, J., Coello, F., & Sardans, J. (2023). A better use of fertilizers is needed for global food security and environmental sustainability. In *Agriculture and Food Security* (Vol. 12, Issue 1). BioMed Central Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40066-023-00409-5>
- Ruf, J., Emberger-Klein, A., & Menrad, K. (2022). Consumer response to bio-based products – A systematic review. In *Sustainable Production and Consumption* (Vol. 34, pp. 353–370). Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.09.022>
- Saddler, J., Ebadian, M., & Mcmillan, J. D. (2020). *Advanced Biofuels-Potential for Cost Reduction*.
- Salazar Sandoval, S., Amenábar, A., Toledo, I., Silva, N., & Contreras, P. (2024). Advances in the Sustainable Development of Biobased Materials Using Plant and Animal Waste as Raw Materials: A Review. In *Sustainability (Switzerland)* (Vol. 16, Issue 3). Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su16031073>
- Serrano-Aguirre, L., & Prieto, M. A. (2024). Can bioplastics always offer a truly sustainable alternative to fossil-based plastics? *Microbial Biotechnology*, 17(4). <https://doi.org/10.1111/1751-7915.14458>
- Sharma, B. P., Yu, T. E., English, B. C., Boyer, C. N., & Larson, J. A. (2020). Impact of government subsidies on a cellulosic biofuel sector with diverse risk preferences toward feedstock uncertainty. *Energy Policy*, 146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.111737>
- Singh, N., Ogunseitan, O. A., Wong, M. H., & Tang, Y. (2022). Sustainable materials alternative to petrochemical plastics pollution: A review analysis. In *Sustainable Horizons* (Vol. 2). Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.horiz.2022.100016>
- UNOSD. (2024). *The Waste Crisis: Accelerating National to Local Policy Action Evidence-based strategies for sustainable solutions*. <https://desapublications.un.org/publications/waste-crisis-accelerating-national-local-policy-action-evidence-based-strategies>
- Vejendla, L. C., Janaki, P., Parameswari, E., Suganthi, M., Krishnan, R., & Meena, S. (2025). Harnessing regenerative agriculture for climate change mitigation: a comprehensive review and meta-analysis. *Discover Agriculture*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44279-025-00266-9>
- Velasquez, S. T. R., Hu, Q., Kramm, J., Santin, V. C., Völker, C., & Wurm, F. R. (2025). Plastics of the Future? An Interdisciplinary Review on Biobased and Biodegradable Polymers: Progress in Chemistry, Societal Views, and Environmental Implications. In *Angewandte Chemie - International Edition* (Vol. 64, Issue 23). John Wiley and Sons Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202423406>

- Villat, J., & Nicholas, K. A. (2023). Quantifying soil carbon sequestration from regenerative agricultural practices in crops and vineyards. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2023.1234108>
- Wang, W., Wang, Y., Zhang, X., & Zhang, D. (2021). Effects of government subsidies on production and emissions reduction decisions under carbon tax regulation and consumer low-carbon awareness. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(20). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph182010959>
- Weinrich, R., & Herbes, C. (2023). Consumer research on bioplastics: A systematic review. *Q Open*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.1093/qopen/qoad013>
- Weiss, M., Haufe, J., Carus, M., Brandão, M., Bringezu, S., Hermann, B., & Patel, M. K. (2012). A Review of the Environmental Impacts of Biobased Materials. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 16(SUPPL.1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1530-9290.2012.00468.x>
- Wellenreuther, C., Wolf, A., & Zander, N. (2021). *Cost structure of bio-based plastics: A Monte-Carlo-Analysis for PLA*. <https://bioplasticseurope.eu/>
- Wu, J., Wang, J., Zeng, Y., Sun, X., Yuan, Q., Liu, L., & Shen, X. (2024). Biodegradation: the best solution to the world problem of discarded polymers. In *Bioresources and Bioprocessing* (Vol. 11, Issue 1). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40643-024-00793-1>
- Zaborowska, M., & Bernat, K. (2023). The development of recycling methods for bio-based materials – A challenge in the implementation of a circular economy: A review. In *Waste Management and Research* (Vol. 41, Issue 1, pp. 68–80). SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X221105432>
- Zuiderveen, E. A. R., Kuipers, K. J. J., Caldeira, C., Hanssen, S. V., van der Hulst, M. K., de Jonge, M. M. J., Vlysidis, A., van Zelm, R., Sala, S., & Huijbregts, M. A. J. (2023). The potential of emerging bio-based products to reduce environmental impacts. *Nature Communications*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-43797-9>

worm

**Waste in humanitarian Operations:
Reduction and Minimisation**

Funded by the
European Union